

TEACHER ACCOUNTABILITY SYSTEM

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The teacher should be Accountable is a which,in the public mind has assumed sufficient importance. The National policy on Education states that norms for he Accountability of teachers should be developed.In the programme of Action formulated for implementing for their social and professional responsibilities.Before this,Accountability was never questioned.The accountability should start with them alone.

Accountability :

“Accountability means responsility for something and to someone.”

Accountbilty means;

Accountibility means responsibility for something and to someone.there are well defined goals and accountability implies a continuous assessment procedure to weigh outputs in relation to the expected goals and to indicate and explain the discrepancies if any.

Accountibility actually is nothing out the process of goals,providing adequate measures to achieve those goals and conducting regular evaluations to find out whether the predefined goals could be achieved or not.

The two prerequisites of accountability are:

1) Auditing:

Auditing means looking into the records of work done.In the educational field auditing was used only to look into financial matters.But for teachers accountabilitiy too,auditing can assess the teachers work in the context of his well- defined role and pupils achievements.

2) Continuous Evaluation

The teachers appraisal should be a continupus process It should not be done at the

end of the session or after an interval of 4 to 5 year at the time of teacher to a higher grade. Continuous evaluation of the teachers work can help a great deal in providing proper feedback for the improvement of the improvement of the teachers performance.

- i) A comprehensive system of teacher evaluations should be created.
- ii) It should be data based.
- iii) Incentives and disincentives should be provided on the basis of evaluation.

Teacher Accountability system

Teacher accountability system should be comprehensive enough to encompass all the aspects

- I. It is said that whenever a teachers appraisal system existed in the past,
- II. It was often used as a punishment device. Teachers accountability system should be devised actually for giving incentives for good performance and disincentives for non-performance. So teachers accountability for what can be.
- III. It should evaluate multiple criteria viz, Teachers content knowledge and teaching skill.
- IV. The teacher should use multiple methods. For evaluation a number of methods, systematic classroom observation by peers and supervisors and self-appraisal should be a regular practice.
- V. The teacher is accountable to a range of people parents, professional colleagues, institutions and the pupils.
- VI. For deciding on rewarding good teachers and for providing disincentives to the incompetent ones.
- VII. For providing feedback to improve teaching. It can be used for diagnostic purpose.

The evaluators can be;

- I. Head-The Head of the Department, the principal or any higher authority is the best person to judge the teachers work.
- II. Peers- The peer teacher can also make an objective assessment of the work

done by their colleagues.

- III. Students- The best judge of any teacher is the student whom he teaches. The students appraisal of the teacher can help a lot in getting a real picture of the work of the teacher.
- IV. defined norms a teacher can know where he stands. Self-appraisal can work wonders. self-appraisal- The teacher can also assess himself. By judging oneself on well in providing feedback to teacher for self-improvement

Conclusions :

Accountability involves a critical analysis of the quality and quantity of how much is being done of what is actually expected to be done. Anyone involved therein is accountable to someone or to a particular system for what is obligatory on his part to do very satisfactorily. Thus, the teacher must know this different roles and work accordingly to the students and to the society.

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